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The Origin and Development of Manuscript Writing in Terāpantha

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Every soul in this universe holds some qualities in itself. The one who recognizes his or her qualities can make his life artistic. It is special to live an artistic life. In Jain religion they even have an artistic approach to attain death. Art is of various types. Some indicate spirituality whereas some express the outer world. But some arts are important which present the creative aspect as well as defend the spiritual aspect hence they are invaluable. One such art is Manuscript writing.

Writing is living history of humanity. Writing is weights and measures of a man's experiences and reflections. It is difficult to tell clearly the time of beginning of script writing. Modern historians believe that script writing began during the Veda period but Jain archeology reaches beyond.

According to Jain archeology the history of manuscripts in India is very old. Lord Ṛṣabha taught script writing and mathematics to both his daughters Brāhmī and Sundarī. Before the 6th century of the Vikram Era the entire Jain and Buddhist literature was passed on verbally from teacher to students. After which Jain Ācārya Śrī Devardhi Gani Kṣamāśramaṇa, bearing the future in mind converted the entire literature formatted by Lord Mahāvīra and narrated to Gaṇadharas, ācāryas and Sthaviras into books. It is difficult to say what was the procedure of paper-making at that time but apparently it was lack of availability of paper that the palm leaves came into the picture. The available ancient manuscripts prove that the art of script writing was par excellence in that era. Along with beautification of the scripts the various ways they used for security and durability matched the reflections and experience of the modern day artists. We can assess from the manuscripts of past one

thousand years that script writing was a major art of some era. The manuscripts of 10th to 12th century are found on palm and bark leaves. It is said that the tradition of writing on paper began around 13th or 14th century. Important contribution has been made by Jain monks and script writers in the field of manuscript writing. Millions of copies are preserved till date in the Jain Bhāṇḍārās. Two traditions came into existence after almost 500-600 years of Lord Mahāvīra. One was Svetāmbara and the other Digambara. One sect of Svetāmbara tradition originated in the form of Terāpantha.

History of Terāpantha is the history of religious revolution. Ācārya Bhikṣu laid the foundation of Terāpantha on the basis of characteristic purity. Terāpantha was established on Vikram samvat 1817 (*Āṣād Pūrṇimā*) (29th June, 1760 AD). Terāpantha was not something established suddenly, but at that point of time it was a demand that was essential and non-prohibitive. That was such time when the Indian population believed more in the blind traditions and conventions. Many types of social and political differences pervaded. Even the religion sector could not stay untouched by the poor conditions. The conduct and thoughts related flabbiness generated a hard to be fulfilled vacuum in the monk societies. Due to all the circumstantial suffocation the seeds germinated of a religious revolution and came afore in the form of Terāpantha.

In Vikram samvat 1817 (Caitra Śuklā Navami) Saint Bhikhan severed his relations with Ācārya Raghunāth Ji. With him Tokar ji, Harnāth ji, Vīrbhān ji and Bharmal ji four saints also followed. Ācārya Bhikhan ji lead and guided this religious revolution. The reestablishment of right conduct and right consideration was the sole purpose. He completely succeeded in that. Initially many people opposed his ideologies strongly but later accepted finding them true and appropriate. Whereas Terāpantha may be called as sunny cure organization for Jain religion, it may also be called the cream of the religious revolution in the field of pure conduct.

Rajasthan stands high when it comes to ancient style of art. The manuscripts found in Kalu, Lunkaransara, Pungala, Suratgarh, Udaipur, Chaadwas and Kheenvsara (Marwar) are most beautiful, clear and visible. Looking at the ancient bhāṇḍārās we can say that those people had strong psychology, seasoned hands and acknowledged thoughts.

Jain artists were accomplished in various art forms such as architecture, craft, scripts etc. They were the jewels of Indian art. If we extract the available Jain literature from Literature stores, it will lose its big portion. Even today Terāpantha presents some excellent specimen of manuscript art.

This research article is an effort to present the discussion in reference to the origination and development of manuscript writing in Terāpantha community.

The history of manuscripts exists from the beginning of Terāpantha. The daily reading and study material and other necessary books were mainly supplemented by hand written books.

Manuscript Writing Equipments

There were various types of equipments used for this art of writing.

Some of the important equipments are-

- Card board for Characters- Character practice board, Plain paper
- Wooden Plank
- Board to draw lines
- Ancient letter of ligature

- Scale
- Wooden unit for writing
- Cloth unit for writing
- *Puttha* (Parcel) in different colors to store Manuscripts

Other than these some more are-

Koda-Kodi-2, Toksi-1, Rejmaal-1, Spoon-1, Shape-1, Pen-3, Ink pot-1, Hinglu in Toksi, Hartāl, Toksi (small container) for ink, Plastic containers-3, White *Hinglu, Hirmich* etc.

The Usage of Writing Equipments and the Technique of Writing :

A unique lore is used for manuscript writing in Terāpantha community which is used at different levels – to learn there has been a tradition to initially practice by writing on sand. After which they write with ‘*Khadi*’ (chalk like white soil) on wooden planks. In Terāpantha tradition they have unique method to practice alphabets. In the beginning the writer is made to practice on sand spread on the ground. When he masters that then he is given a plank or a board. This included a thin card board on which letters are written with black ink is given to the practitioner. On which he places a thin paper and writes characters on characters. Gradually when his hand is set with the ink he is given papers and by practicing on the rough papers he grows into a beautiful writer.

Starch is used on the fabric and tied with threads gradually to maintain straight lines while scribing. The threads are tied at equal distance. It is then polished with varnish to keep the threads intact. This set is called ‘*Phantion ki Patri*’ (a board to draw lines). The writer takes a plain paper and places it lawfully over this board. He holds it tightly with one hand and applies pressure on the threads with the other hand. The threads emboss on the paper. It forms straight line marks. The writer follows the marks to write. This way the lines are aligned, beautiful and uniform. If you use pencils to rule out the lines it leaves marks behind, rubbing them destroys the neatness of the letters. Hence this is an easy

way to solve all difficulties. '*Phantiyon ki Patri*' is also artistic. The instruments used too are artistically made which is again a speciality.

To avoid sweat while writing they keep a small card board. This is also handmade. The monks do not use tables and chairs as the modern writers. Their writing office stays with them everywhere in the village or town.

They sit on their heels. The knees are upwards and straight. There is a wooden plank placed on the knees with a layer of double folded cloth over it. They place the lined paper over it. To avoid sweat clips are placed on top. To save the paper from flying due to the winds they fix it with two clips. Even though the clips are handmade its art and utility is clearly visible. One up and one down two incisions are made on a piece of bamboo. Two small herbage sections are stuffed into both the incisions. When you press the incised part with hand, the other incision opens and that becomes our ancient port.

The writer also keeps a pen stand with him which is hand made by sticking using '*Lhai*' (gum) of fabric. Pen stand is beautiful and long-lasting. There are 5-7 pens, 2-3 '*Pichhis*', Bamboo sticks, whitener in a small wooden '*Topsi*', '*Hartāl*' in one and dissolved '*Hinglu*' in a bigger '*Topsi*'. While writing if due to negligence the writer makes a mistake, he uses white color or '*Hartāl*' dissolved in little water as cover up. The letter is subordinated by the color. It is rubbed after dying and new letter is written over it. It helps to maintain the lines and the blank space does not look unsightly. It keeps up the beauty of the letter. Usually there is a tradition to apply '*Hartāl*' on white and yellow paper. While writing manuscript any wrong alphabet or any mistake was covered up by applying '*Hartāl*.' '*Koda and Kodi*' -these two equipments were used. '*Kodi*' was used to smoothen the letters deleted by '*Hartāl*' and '*Koda*' was used to smoothen the paper before writing.

A separate method is followed for the type of ink or the kind of ink used to script. Generally black ink was used for writing which was usually prepared by hand. Almond rinds were burned to prepare the soot from

which they made the ink. Ink is there after churned with an adhesive paste to make it stronger and long lasting. The monks do not leave the ink wet overnight. They pour all the ink in a container and leave a cloth in it. The cloth blots the entire ink. The next day they pour water on it and squeeze back the ink. The squeezed ink is poured in an inkstand. Inkstand too is done creatively. It's a small ink stand made of wood which we call '*Kumpla*'. Despite using fresh ink every time one cannot make out that two types of ink has been used. This is an art. The parsing, digits, end of chapter etc. are marked with red ink (*Hinglu*). '*Hinglu*' is the red ink that was used for important characters while writing manuscripts. It doubled the beauty of the paper written in black ink. Some verses are painted with golden '*Hirmich*'. '*Hirmich*' is a kind of a highlighter which is used to highlight important characters and heading etc. There is red line on both sides known as '*Phantia*'. The scale to draw '*Phantia*' is also handmade. It is a long scale made of wood which is thinned at one edge, the other being normal. They keep the normal edge upwards. Due to thinning the lower edge remains above the paper and forms the base for '*Phantia*'. The blank portion on top of the paper is called '*Jihvā*'. In the free area on both sides the name of the copy is written on one side and the number is mentioned on the other.

To keep the scribed leaves safe the writer uses a '*Puttha*'. '*Puttha*' is made of fabric. It is ideal to save the paper from folds and rains etc. To avoid the sweat from the hands of the student, a green and a white, two rails are formed. The green is made of paper and the white of fabric usually. They too are artistically made. There is a wooden scale on the papers which saves the paper from the thumb.

Ink, *Hinglu*, *Hartāl*, Whitener, *Hirmich*, Ink Pot, Bowl, *Topsi* for *Hinglu* and Whitener, *Pichi* (Plastic pipe to delete the characters), Plank, Rails, *Puttha*, Clips, *Kami*, *Phatiyon ki Patri*, Pen stand, Pens, Spoon made of pine nut rind to add water to the ink, all the material required by the writer is prepared by hands. According to the management of the organization all these are made by the nuns.

The characters printed by machines may be darker or lighter, bigger or smaller, distant or closer but not in these letters. These hand written papers are much better than the printed ones. Another specialty of hand written papers is that the writer leaves blank spaces in between known as '*Bawdi*'. '*Bawdi*' is an art specimen too.

In canonical literature the main text is written in bold font and they write the '*Tabba*' (Interpretation) above the text in tiny letters. The method to write accurate canonical literature is in a different manner and the letters are written in a different manner. The prayers are written in a different style. There is a separate design to write '*Chūrni*' and '*Pañjikā*' (Register). Some papers have the main in bold font, Sanskrit print in red and the '*Tika*' in intricate characters.

Three types of paper were used for scribing - 1. *Kashmiri* Paper, 2. *Chamariya* paper and 3. *Niliya* paper. Of these *Niliya* papers last for more than 500 years and are called from London. The pens are generally made of Baru or Cinnamon trees. In Terāpantha you do not find manuscripts on cloth or gold illuminated letters. Neither you find them on palm and bark leaves nor written by paid professional scribes. But there is one house holder known to earn a living mainly by writing manuscripts that is disciple Ganesh Das Ji Matheran (Vikram era 1917-1992, 1860-1935 AD). Samvat 1956-1962 (1899-1905AD) He stayed with his uncle Mahatma Bhairondaan Ji in Bikaner. There he began scribing professionally and sold his scribes through Ranjitmal Ji Bachhawat to Jain institutions and other people. It is said that he translated approximately 4 lakh verses. He sold his copies in Madhya Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, Haryana, Delhi, Punjab, Gujarat and other states. He even purchased and sold old books. He took orders to write and sell when travelling to the above mentioned states. Even the parents of the Jain monks asked him to write books and bought books from him time and again.

After the brief introduction of the art of writing in Terāpantha, various equipments and their usage, we will now discuss the contributions made by monks and nuns in Terāpantha tradition in the field of manuscript writing-

Primitive promoter of Terāpantha Ācārya Bhikhan Ji Swami was a sagem of highest category. Not only was he a philosopher, a poet, a writer but also an efficient artist. He increased the zest of his successor Ācārya Bharmal Ji towards the art of script writing. His experience was – Art cannot be developed without practicing writing. He used to hold hands and teach how to write. The letters set automatically as you practice writing. Ācārya Bhikshu himself wrote numerous books. In his life-span he created approximately 38000 verses which were scripted by Ācārya Bharmal Ji. The original copies of which are still the soul of Terāpantha organization. Bhikhan Ji swami was the first script write of Terāpantha. He was a script practitioner long before his ordination in Terāpantha. '*Āvaśyaka sūtra*' is available of the first copies written by Swami Ji. It was written in (1754 AD). Big and small copies of (1755-56 AD) era are also available. Ācārya Bhikshu copied '*Sthānāṅga Sūtra*' and '*Sutrakritāṅga*' along with its *Tabba*.

FIG-2.

FIG-3.

Transcription of '*Sthānāṅga Sūtra*' by Ācārya Bhikshu It holds the

dignity of being the first copy in Terāpantha in manuscript domain. Due to

being old and chronic in condition these manuscripts have been specially laminated sans plastic for safety. From the time of Ācārya Bhikshu monk society has been encouraged to write and excel in manuscript writing. Once in the initial stage Muni Hemraaj Ji Swami wrote a letter and showed it to Swami Ji, In that the lines were uneven. Swami Ji laughed and said “ when a farmer ploughs the land he tries to keep the plough straight and you have written uneven even on a piece of paper. To enhance your script writing you have to focus on writing in straight lines”. After which Muni Bharmal Ji (second Ācārya) created beautiful manuscripts of verses on different topics written by Ācārya Bhikshu. Other than these he also scripted *Rāma carita*, *Ṛṣabha caritra*, *Jambu Kumār*, *Ninhava Ro Rasa*, *Menraya Ki Chaupai*, *Shatibhadhra* and many other narrations and verses.

FIG-4.

Transcription of ‘Ninhava Ro Rasa’ by Ācārya Bharmal Ji

The time of creation of these manuscripts is estimated Samvat 1849(1792 AD). During the period of the third Ācārya Raichand Ji Swami many monks were creating manuscripts. Rishi Raj Ji himself created 713 leaves of ‘*Bhagwati Sūtra Tabba*’ in clean letters for the first time around Samvat 1877 (1820 AD). Another was written in beautiful letters in Samvat 1864 (1807 AD) on *Asoj Sudi Ashtami*, Tuesday, a copy of *Daśawaikālika Tabba* in 42 folia by Raichand Ji.

FIG-5

Transcription of *Daśawaikālika Tabba* by Ācārya Raichand Ji (Last Leaf)

After this numerous monks and nuns created manuscripts of *Bhagwati Sūtra*. In Vikram era 1897 (1840 AD) in the city of Borawar Muni Jivraj Ji created history by writing entire *Bhagwati Sūtra* in just 40 leaves. Of all the texts written till then in Terāpantha this was predominantly the minutest. He used to write with both hands.

During the period of fourth Ācārya there was a lot of development for beautification of scripts. When he was looking for elements to attract the script writers permanently, to keep them motivated to improvise their letters. He wanted the monks to write beautiful letters. For that Jayāchārya himself began configuration of letters on the basis of ancient copies. He improvised his script practicing on a beautiful copy done by an ascetic. The scriptwriters felt a new zeal in their endeavor when Jayāchārya introduced the sonnet system. During his reign many monks spent time writing manuscripts. He with Sati Das Ji Swami completed the transcription of *Bhagwati Sūtra* with *Tabba* in Samvat 1889 (1832 AD). Most importantly during his reign manuscript writing developed a lot in nun-society too. Firstly Sadhvi Meranji wrote *Bhagwati Sūtra*. After that Gulaban Ji (Sister of Maghwa Gani) in Samvat 1926 (1869 AD) wrote ‘*Bhagwati Jod*’ (Jayāchārya krita) in 475 leaves with 63790 verses. In the history of manuscripts no written text as big as this by nun-society is

heard of. It is a record in itself. At the same time Muni Kalu Ji (Railmagra) also wrote '*Bhagwati Jod*' in 531 leaves and Muni Shri Kundan mal Ji with Sadhvi Khooman Ji (Ladnun) also copied it. All the four copies are now safe in the book stores. After which the monks and nuns almost competed to write manuscripts. Other than this each group had to create 25 sonnets per day as tax till he is on post. They even related work with sonnets. This is how the sequence grew to write manuscripts. That's how the 'Sonnets system' promoted by Jayāchārya proved significant for Terāpantha sect. Foreseer and great thinker Jayāchārya, on the basis of said project not only improved script writing of the organization but also presented an ideal system by publicizing the private collection of books. Terāpantha by that scheme gained good script writers, good books, proper distribution and proper utilization of things. The sonnet system was popularly in effect till Samvat 2027 (1862 AD). It was discontinued after that. Due to easy availability of printed books, the hand written became unnecessary. The said system was source of inspiration for various works for about more than 100 years.

FIG-6.

***Bhagwati Ki Jod* created by Jayacharya, Leaf 475, Year 1926**

Once Ācārya Bhikshu Swami came to Gogunda. He found a copy of *Bhagwati Sūtra* in the Porwal temple. Copy was very alluring and artistically made. The leaf count was 1800 and it weighed approx. 9 ser (i.e. 8.39790kg). The voluminous copy of *Bhagwati* is still safe and adorns the Terāpantha Depository. Jayāchārya conceived a novel idea

from that copy. On the basis of this script he taught script writing to heir-apparent Maghwā Gaṇi. That is the beginning of new series of script writing in Terāpantha. Scripts of Maghwā Gaṇi were clear, beautiful and immaculate. He added another chapter in script art by writing minute characters. The minute the character, it is less of paper hence lighter.

The fifth Ācārya of Terāpantha organization Maghraj Ji Swami was an excellent script writer. The texts written by him clearly indicate his accomplished character formation. He established his individual importance in beautiful and intricate writing. He set a record by writing the entire '*Anuttaropapatika Sūtra*' along with its recension on a leaf 11" inch long and 5" broad. He scribed on various topics like *Caritra*, *Caupāiya*, *Duhā*, *Ārāadhanā* etc. from Samvat 1929-1940 (1872-1883 AD) in Rajasthani language.

FIG-7.

Hand script by fifth Ācārya of Terāpantha Maghwā Gaṇi

Not much description is found related to manuscript writing in period of sixth Ācārya Mānak Gaṇi except one of his hand written manuscript in *Tulsi Kalā Prekshā* (Ladnun).

FIG-8.

Manuscript by Jambu Kumār, Ācārya Mānak Gaṇi, VSYear 1836

In relevance to hand written manuscript copies not much is known about of era of seventh Ācārya Dāl Gaṇi.

The maximum work of manuscript scribing in Terāpantha took place during the reign of eighth Ācārya Kālu Gaṇi and ninth Ācārya Shri Tulsi. Kālu Gaṇi himself was a master.

FIG-9.

Writing skill of Ācārya Kālu Gaṇi

During Samvat 1951-66 (1894-1909 AD) Kālu Gaṇi not only enriched the text depositories by his manuscripts but also training young monks and nuns wrote on hundreds of card boards and planks where they starting

with trembling hands gradually reached the peak of beautiful script art. Also he encouraged hundreds of monks and nuns and collected thousands of manuscripts in Prakrit, Sanskrit and Rajasthani. There are more than 5500 manuscripts written by saints and vestals. These include Canonical Literature, Sanskrit Grammar, Jurisprudence, Poetic couplet Literature and collection of hundreds of Rajasthani narrations. During the reign of Ācārya Tulsi, and Mahāprajña they began editing Canonical Literature on the basis of base manuscripts and books of other philosophies. It is constantly on-going till date.

FIG-10.

FIG-11.

Hand written copies by Ācārya Shri Tulsi

FIG-12.

Hand written copies by Ācārya Mahāprajña

The reign of Ācārya Tulsi Samvat 1966-1993 (1909-1936 AD) saw speedy development in the field of script art. 90% of monks and nuns were manuscript writers. Hundreds of copies were written and exchanged on occasion of *Māgh Mahotsav* which would become a memorable picture. On Vikram Era 2002 (1945 AD) on *Śrāvan Shuklā 5* in *Bhiwani*, *Muni Shri Nemichand Ji* presented a paper with constant effort of 50 days. It has 106 lines on one side. Each line has 344 letters. Śloka count is 2300. Writing 72000 characters on a leaf 9 ¼ by 4 ¼ inches is really incredible.

Muṇi Shri Jaskaran ji, *Muni Shri Aaskaran Ji*, *Muni Shri Manmal Ji* wrote 700 ślokas each on single folia. *Muni Shri Sohanlal Ji* also attained good skill in minute script. Many saints have written 1 lakh to 3 lakh verses. Some of the important names in this are *Muni Maganlal Ji*, *Muni Kundanmal Ji (Javad)*, *Muni Jivanmal Ji (Jasol)*, *Muni Kevalchand ji*, *Muni Sohanlal Ji (Churu)*, *Muni Manmal Ji* etc. Along with beautifying the script *Muni Kundanmal Ji (Javad)* even applied intricate work and attained unprecedented success. He wrote entire '*Daśawaikālikā Sūtra*' on one leaf, '*Vipāksūtra*' on another. In Samvat 1977 (1920 AD) the four monthly sojourn of Kālu Gaṇi was in Bhiwani. *Muni Shri Kundanmal Ji* too was serving his master. There he

engraved' *Uttarādhyayana*' and '*Vyāvahara Culikā Sūtra*' in a miniature leaf of about 4x8 inches with 2500 verses comprising of 80 thousand characters. He holds a unique position in the history of script art. He only used pens made of Baru tree to write.

Another saint from the Tulsi era *Muni Kundanmal Ji* (Barar) had good capability to create maps. He created map of India after his ordination. His script writing was remarkable. He wrote numerous copies. '*Uttarādhyayana Sūtra*' created by him has picture on both sides of the margin. His manuscript is the only one found with pictures.

Muni Harakhlal Ji (Harsh Lal ji Lachuda) encouraged script art and wrote more than 500 leaves (Both sides). He practiced intricate characters and in Samvat 2018 (1961 AD) wrote complete '*Gītā*' on a leaf. He wrote 10 such leaves. Also two leaves of '*Sambhodhi*' and '*Daśawaikālikā Sūtra*' (Comprising of 1000 verses) on each leaf.

FIG-13.

FIG-14.

Complete 'Gītā' on one leaf.

The hand script of tenth Ācārya Mahāprajña Ji was not impressive. The scripts of coeval and fellow saints were beautiful and well formed. But Ācārya Mahāprajña lacked in this aspect. Ācārya Kālu Gaṇi saw his script, smiled but did not comment. Sitting besides *Muni Shri Magan Ji* commented- “*Kanwar Sahab ka akshar to daagle sukhave jisa hai*”. (The characters are as crooked as the cow dung left out to dry on terrace). Ācārya Mahāprajña felt embarrassed. That gave birth to a yearning in his mind. Period of time even his script improved. After some time in Vikram Samvat 1991-92 Ācārya Mahāprajña wrote ‘*Pārśvanātha stotra*’ and presented it before *Muni Tulsi*. He saw, patted his back and said “Your characters have now become okay.” Not much is known in context of manuscript writing of present Ācārya Mahā Śramaṇa.

Terāpantha saints contribute exclusively even in the field of art. First drawings found are datable approx. 150 years old done by *Bhawan Ji Swāmi*. In which ‘*Loknal*’ and ‘*Nairāyiks*’ were pictured in ancient technique. Even today the colors are bright and intact. After which *Muni Dulichand Ji* (Pachpadra) used new techniques to draw ‘*Nairāyiks*’ and other educational pictures. His colleague *Muni Sagarmal Ji Shraman* drew many pictures as well. These paintings are safely deposited in ‘*Tulsi Kalā Prekshā*’ (Jain Vishwa Bharati University, Ladnun). He beautifully wrote ‘*Abhidhāna Cintāmaṇi*’ (*Prākṛit Koṣa*) prepared by Hemchandracharya in 26 folia and many others too.

FIG-15.

Muni Sohanlāl Ji swāmi had amazing expertise in writing, drawing and crafts. He wrote numerous copies in beautiful characters. He created many emotive pictures. He created many artistic things like wooden and plastic watch, sun –clock and meter to measure eye glass power. The drawings by disciplines were used traditionally to write poetry. One of which is artistic poetry. The monks and nuns of Jain Terāpantha too followed this tradition. Almost 100 years ago *Muni Chandmal Ji* ordained by fifth *Ācārya Maghwā Gaṇi* created art depicted poetry comprising of 163 drawings and minute characters by which the poetry is written. These are based on *Chhatrabaddha*, *Mukutbaddha*, *Phool*, *Hār*, *Vrikṣa*, *Dwār*, *Narakar* etc. stanzas and *Saptbhuji Naag Prabandh*, *Chhappay Ekakshari Chhand*, *Ekakshari Shikharani*, *Katarbanddh Rola Chhand* etc. pictures. There are three chariots, bull, deer, horse with one sonnet written in each of them from which 18000 sonnets can be created of each. All these colored pictures are done by hand.

The art depicted poetry created by Muni Chāndmal Ji

In 2000 AD *Sādhi Kalplatā Ji* beautifully copied all the work done by *Ācārya Shri Tulsi*. *Muni Sumermal (Sudarshan)* has written ‘*Ācārya Bhāṣyam*’ (Sanskrit) (2056 AD) by *Ācārya Mahāprajña Ji*, Hindi epic poetry ‘*Rṣabhāyan*’ and Canonical Literature ‘*KalpaSūtra*’ along with its textual variant, ‘*Rājaprasniya*’ and ‘*Uttarādhyayaṇa*’.

Of these ‘*Rīśbhāyana*’, ‘*Kalpasūtra*’ and ‘*Uttaradhyayana*’ have been adorned by beautiful paintings done by Manju Nahata (Kolkata) which makes them more significant.

FIG-17-1.

FIG-17-2.

FIG-17-3.

Beautiful portraiture on manuscripts by Dr. Manju Nahata

This collection is compiled in *Ladnun Seva Kendra*. The indexing is done which holds approximately 5500 manuscripts. On the basis of topic and literature they are divided in 245 categories which are mainly 32 Canonical Literature with their interpreted texts (with *Rajasthani Tabba*). Besides these miscellaneous scriptures by *Ācāryas*, written by *Ācārya* Bhikshu and other *Ācāryas* Siddhapāhud, Painnag, Danadi Pancāśikā, Gautam Kulkam, *Prācīn Āgama*, Sanskrit and prakrit texts handwritten by *Ācāryas* and saints, *Śānt Sudharas*, *Sindūr prakār*, *Bhaktāmara*, *Dr̥ṣṭānta Śataka*, *Jain Siddhānta Dīpikā*, *Nyāya*

Karṇikā, *Vyākaraṇa* (Sanskrit and Prakrit) *Koṣa* (Nāma mālā), *Bhramvidhvansan Kumati Vihandan*, *Sandeh Vishoshadhi*, *Jinagy Mukhamaṇḍan*, *Praśnottar sārḍha Śatak*, *Praśnottar Tattvabodha*, *Bhagwati ki Jod* (Rajasthani) , *Siddhāntasar*, *Raskalā*, *Hundia*, *Ācāraṅgā Jod*, *Jode Vividh Sutro Ki*, *Bhikṣudr̥ṣṭānt*, *Bhikṣu Granthāvali*, *Chaupāiya*, *Jhini Carcā*, *Navbaad*, *Prācīn patra*, *Etihasik Likhat*, *Jayagrantha* (New and Old), *Katharatna Kosh*, *Thokda*, *Bhikṣu Jash Rasāyāna*, *Kālu Yaśovilas*, *Agni parikṣā*, *Gurudev Tulsi ke vyakhyana*, *Muni Sohan ki Rachanaye*, *Vividh Vyākhyāna*, *Kathā Prabandh*, *Prāstāvik Aupedeśik*, *Bhaṣā Śloka Sāgar*, *Saiksha Shiksha*, *Ahimsa Tattvadarśan*, *Vedic Vicār Vimarśa*, *Awadhan etc.*, *Kriṣṇa Bawni*, *Purātan Itihās*, *Parampara ki Jod*, *Maryadavali*, *Katha Drishtanta*, *Sant Satiyon ki Nāmāvali*, *Karṇikā*, *Putha Rāj Ka*, *Jain darśan main prachalit nyāya*, *Yog evam Darśan ke Granth*, *Caritra*, *Mahākavya*, *Jain Kāvya* (Meghdūt, *Kumārsambhava etc.*), *Āgam Atthuttari Nīti Grantha*, *Stotra*, *Stavan*, *Stuti etc.* All of which are written in Sanskrit, Prakrit and Rajasthani languages.

Conclusively we can say that from the primitive promoter of Terāpantha *Ācārya* Bhikshu of Terāpantha community in Swetāmbara tradition to *Ācārya* Mahāprajña, there has been a successive development in the art of manuscript writing. *Ācārya* Bhikshu was enriched with script art long before his ordination in Terāpantha. *Ācārya* Shri Jeetmal Ji introduced the sonnet system. *Ācārya* Maghwā encouraged development of intricate along with beautiful writing. During the reign of *Ācārya* Kālu Gaṇi and *Ācārya* Tulsi there was rapid development in the art of manuscript writing.

This art developed in Terāpantha community not only rejuvenated the ancient literature but also effectually protected and promoted them. Which made contribution in the development of Indian literature, culture and calligraphy?

In the late 20th century the art of manuscript writing slowed down. The biggest reason of which was availability of press. Hence the art of manuscript writing is deteriorating by the day

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2. Information rendered by Muni Sumermal Ji (Sudarshan) (16th july, 25th December 2012, chhapar, Rajasthan).
3. Muni Shramanasagar , *Terāpantha ka Lipi Kaushal va anya Kalaen*, Ācārya Bhikshu Smritigranth, p.224.
4. Ibid p.226-227.
5. Information by Muni Sumermal Ji (Sudarshan).
6. *Terāpantha Ka Itihaas*, Part-6, pp.96-97.
7. Muni Shramanasagar , *Terāpantha ka Lipi Kaushal va anya Kalaen*, Ācārya Bhikshu Smritigranth, p.224
8. Terapantha originated from Sthanakvasis. One of the 22 disciples of Acharya Dharmdas Ji was Dhanno Ji. His third heir was Acharya Raghunath Ji. Promoter of Terapantha Acharya Bhikshu was ordained (1st ordination) by him. *Terāpantha Ka Itihaas* , Chapter -1, p.14.
9. *Terāpantha Ka Itihaas*, Part-2, p.260.
10. Ibid, p. 260.
11. *Jay Smriti*, p.108.
12. *Hastlikhit Granth Suchipatra*, p.81.
13. *Hastlikhit Granth Suchipatra*, P.1.
14. Information derived from hand printed Scanning CD No.829 at Ladnun *Vardhaman Granthagar*, Jain Vishwa Bharati University.
15. *Hastlikhit Granth Suchipatra*, p.1 and *Terapantha Ka Itihaas*, Part-4, p.96.

16. ‘*Gāthā*’ is a classical term and refers to particular verse. But Jayacharya has used it to imply prose comprising of 32 characters or any single verse. He popularized Sonnet system by establishing a rule that the sonnets written by the saint will be deposited in thy name but the handwriting and the text should be approved by the Acharya, *Terapantha Ka Itihaas*, Part-1, p.367.

17. *Hastlikhit Granth Suchipatra*, p.1.

18. Jayacharya began to verse the largest Canonical Literature Bhagwati sutra in Samvat 1919 (1862 AD) in Rajasthani language. He would create extempore verses and Gulabsati would hear it and write it. Jayacharya completed *Bhagwati Ki Jod* in Samvat 1924 (1867 AD) on Poush Sudi 10 in Bidasar, Shashan Samudra, Part-9, p.26.

19. *Hastlikhit Granth Suchipatra*, P.57.

20. *Shaasan Samudra*, Part-9, p.26.

21. *Terāpantha Ka Itihaas*, Part-1, p.367.

22. *Terāpantha Ka Itihaas*, Part-2, p.14.

23. *Hastlikhit Granth Suchipatra*, pp.83-84.

24. *Terāpantha Ka Itihaas*, Part-2, p.261.

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26. Muni Shramansagar, *Terāpantha ka Lipi Kaushal va anya Kalaen*, Ācārya Bhikshu Smritigrah, p.225.

27. *Ibid*, p.225.

28. Particulars in *Terāpantha Ka Itihaas*, complete edition.

29. *Terāpantha Ka Itihaas*, Part-4, p.141.

30. *Terāpantha Ka Itihaas*, Part-2, p.261.

31. *Shashan Samudra*, Part -17, p.123.

32. *Shashan Samudra*, Part -18, p.54.

33. *Mahātmā Mahāprajña*, Yuvacharya Mahashrana, p. 48, 2009.

34. *Shashan Samudra*, Part-14, p. 601.

35. *Terāpantha Ka Itihaas*, Part-4, pp.122-124.

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Paintings conferred by Dr. Manju Nahata

Information rendered by Muni Sumermal Ji (Sudarshan). Mahāvīra, represent some of the oldest and most important extant epigraphical records of the Jains.

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Elephantology in Ancient Jain Literature and Culture

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Introduction

Elephants have played a prominent part in Eastern cultures from ancient times. In Asia, elephants have been used for transport, logging, war and religious purposes. They have fascinated humans for millennia and a vast literature related to their characteristics, diseases and their treatment developed in eastern cultures. The importance of elephant in war made their management very important for kings and a lot of literature on Elephant capture, training and Elephant husbandry came into existence in Sanskrit, the ancient language of India. All known texts agree in attributing knowledge of elephants to the Sage Pālākāpya¹. Apart from him, among the other ancient authorities referred to are Vīrasena, Bṛhaspati, Nīlakaṇṭha, Vyāsa, Nārada, Rājaputra and Vaiśampāyana. Indian poets have also described the behavior of Elephants in many of their works. However, there do exist still several elephant treatises in various manuscript repositories in India as well as in collections of various libraries outside India that are yet to be published and largely remain unknown.

Brief Overview of Earlier Sanskrit and Other Regional Elephant Treatises

Maharṣi Pālākāpya's treatise titled the '*Hastyāyurveda*'² is an elaborate text in the form of a discourse dealing extensively with elephant diseases and their remedies. It runs to about 20,000 or more

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